

WIRELESS WORLD

RESEARCH FORUM

OUTLOOK

Visions and research directions for the Wireless World

November 2009, No 5

A large, semi-transparent blue circle with a radial gradient from light blue at the center to a darker blue at the edge. Inside this circle is a smaller, solid white circle. The text 'Spectrum Sensing and Fragmentation' is centered within the white circle.

Spectrum Sensing and
Fragmentation

Document 5A/???-E

16 November 2009

English only

<the Director, BR>¹

RESPONSE LIAISON ON THE INVITATION FOR CONTRIBUTIONS
IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AN ITU-R REPORT ON COGNITIVE
RADIO SYSTEMS IN THE MOBILE SERVICE

WWRF would like to thank ITU-R WP 5A for the liaison statement on "Invitation for contributions in the development of an ITU-R Report on cognitive radio systems in the mobile service".

WWRF is studying cognitive radio systems and wishes to offer the attached paper entitled <Spectrum Sensing and Fragmentation>.

WWRF would like to continue collaborating with ITU-R WP 5A on this topic, and to provide further relevant results when available.

Electronic attachment: <WWRF_WG8_Spectrum_WhitePaper2.doc>

¹ This contribution was developed in WWRF.

WWRF WG8 on Spectrum Topics

White Paper

Spectrum Sensing and Fragmentation

Editor:

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Version 1.0

10 November 2009

This contribution is partly based on work performed in the framework of the WWRF. It represents the views of the authors(s) and not necessarily those of the WWRF.

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The authors would like to thank the Wireless World Research Forum (WWRF) for the creative and innovative environment that led to this publication.

Spectrum Sensing and Fragmentation

Abstract –

Wireless World Research Forum, WWRF is a global research oriented organization that aims to develop and nurture a long-term vision of the wireless world. It provides a global platform for discussion of research results and for exchange of views to initiate global co-operation towards systems beyond the current ones.

According to the WWRF Vision the key aspects of the future wireless world are fulfilling user needs and enhancing user experience through, ultra-high bit rates, ubiquitous coverage via heterogeneous access, low cost and machine-to-machine and sensor networks. Spectrum for communications is seen by the WWRF as an important enabling aspect, especially when higher bit rates and new technologies will be required in the future.

The usage of the wireless services continues to increase, both due to the fact that the number of users is increasing, and because the usage and traffic by each individual user grows. It is predicted that by the year 2010 there will be around 2 billion terrestrial mobile subscribers worldwide. New services are coming, which require higher bit rates and hence there will be a need for networks to provide higher capacities and better interference mitigation techniques. To this end, spectrum sensing will become very important for future technologies and services offered by operators. Furthermore, spectrum fragmentation is a further reason that new techniques are needed in order to exploit spectrum gaps and white spaces among the fragmented spectrum assignments. Thus this white paper is focused on these two very important issues (spectrum sensing and fragmentation) innovative techniques and limitations for their development.

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List of Abbreviations

3G	3rd Generation mobile services or systems
A/DC	Analogue to Digital Converter
AGC	Automatic Gain Control
ATSC	Advanced Television Systems Committee
BS	Base Station
CR(S)	Cognitive Radio (Systems)
DFS	Dynamic Frequency Sharing
DSA	Dynamic Spectrum Access
DTV	Digital Television
DVB-T	Digital Video Broadcasting - Terrestrial
FCC	(US) Federal Communications Committee
FFS	Fixed Satellite Service
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FTB	Frequency Tracking Blocks
GSM	Global System for Mobile communications (an ETSI Standard)
HOS	Higher Order Statistics
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (USA)
IF	Intermediate Frequency
IMT-2000	International Mobile Telecommunications - 2000 (an ITU term)
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
ITU-R	International Telecommunications Union - Radiocommunications Sector
LE	License-Exempt
LP – BP	Low Pass – Band Pass
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
PC	Personal Computer
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RF	Radio Frequency
RLAN	Radio Local Area Network
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
TD-SCDMA	Time Division- Synchronous Code Division Multiple Access
TV	Television
UHF	Ultra High Frequency
UMTS	Universal Mobile Telecommunications System
UWB	Ultra Wide Band
VHF	Very High Frequency
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WRC	World Radiocommunication Conference (of the ITU)
WWRF	Wireless World Research Forum

1 Introduction

Wireless World Research Forum, WWRF is a global research oriented organization that aims to develop and nurture a long term vision of the wireless world. It provides a global platform for discussion of research results and for exchange of views to initiate global co-operation towards systems beyond the current ones.

According to the WWRF Vision the key aspects of the future wireless world are fulfilling user needs and enhancing user experience through ultra-high bit rates, ubiquitous coverage via heterogeneous access, low cost and machine-to-machine and sensor networks. Spectrum is seen by the WWRF as an important enabling aspect, especially when higher bit rates and new technologies will be required in the future.

The usage of the wireless services continues to increase, both due to the fact that the number of users is increasing, and because the usage and traffic by an individual user grows. It is predicted that by the year 2010 there will be around 4 billion terrestrial mobile subscribers worldwide [1]. New services are coming, which require higher bit rates and hence there will be a need for networks to provide higher capacities and better interference mitigation techniques. To this end, spectrum sensing will become very important for future technologies and services offered by operators. Furthermore, spectrum fragmentation is a further reason that new techniques are needed in order to exploit the created spectrum gaps and white spaces. Thus this white paper is focused on these two very important issues (spectrum sensing and fragmentation) by investigating innovative techniques and for their development.

Cognitive radio systems (CRS) technologies are being considered in many applications to enable re-use of spectrum “white spaces” and these are addressed in great extent in this paper. In addition to RF sensing, CRS need to be able to combine information from many sources including local regulations, local deployed channel usage, geolocation, and the various thresholds through which the CRS can evaluate the white space channels in its neighborhood.

Future mobile and wireless communications will provide aggregated total throughput data rates up to 100 Mbps for new mobile access and up to 1 Gbps for new nomadic local area access. The expected carrier bandwidth for these data rates is in the order of 100 MHz. However, the outcome of the WRC 2007 does not provide such wide carrier bandwidth with contiguous frequency bands for new radio systems. In this paper some issues for investigation of fragmented spectrum bands are summarized to get a better understanding on the implications of aggregating spectrum assignments.

The paper is organised as follows; chapter 2 discusses the state of the art of spectrum sensing, chapter 3 presents some well-known spectrum sensing techniques for various systems. Chapter 4 gives an insight into the bands available for spectrum sensing and

chapter 5 details the use of Fragmented Frequency Spectrum for Wireless Broadband Communications. Finally, conclusions are provided in chapter 6.

2 State of the Art [of Spectrum Sensing]

The first instance of formal regulatory consideration of spectrum sensing and ‘cognitive radio’ occurred in the consideration by the ITU-R of the re-use of the 5 GHz radiolocation band by license-exempt devices for radio local area networks. In the 5 250-5 350 and 5 470-5 725 MHz bands, new power-limited communications systems were permitted to share the band with the incumbent RADAR systems of the Radiolocation Service. Such sharing is on the condition that proper detection of the primary user is made and that upon detection, the low-power license-exempt (LE) devices would quickly move out of the frequency range used by the RADAR system. For these 5 GHz bands, regulations have been adopted by the ITU (cf. Resolution 229 (WRC-03)) to permit sharing with the aid of a Dynamic Frequency Sharing (DFS) protocol (cf. Recommendation ITU-R M.1652). This protocol specifies the sensing/detection and operational techniques to be used by the power-limited local communications systems to avoid interference to the RADAR systems. This concept has subsequently been expanded to other applications and is finding its way in to other ITU-R Recommendations and, in particular, Recommendation ITU-R M 1797 gives the following definition:

“Cognitive radio system: A radio system that has the capability to sense and be aware of its operational environment, to be trained to dynamically and autonomously adjust its radio operating parameters accordingly and to learn from the results of its actions and environmental usage patterns.”

The technique of RADAR sensing in these 5 GHz band is technically relatively simple because of the high level of the RADAR signals to be detected (detection threshold = -62 dBm). Still, this simple approach at re-using partially fallow spectrum resulted in a lot of discussions at the ITU-R and national levels with ensuing refinements of the sensing schemes to detect specific characteristics of the RADAR signals to make sure that the protection of primary service was ensured.

Since then, cognitive radio systems (CRS) have been considered in many other applications to allow re-use of spectrum “white spaces”. Examples of potential “white spaces” applications include spectrum use within the TV broadcast bands, parts of the 3.5 GHz band (shared with earth stations in the Fixed Satellite Service (FSS) in some countries), and the use of the 5 GHz band by co-primary services (Mobile and Radiolocation services). The stations of the primary service in most of these cases have a fixed location, a fixed area of service coverage and a predictable channel usage. These characteristics help create the opportunity to use this spectrum as white space.

Cognitive radio systems are more challenging if there is no a priori temporal and/or geographical idle space conditions. In this environment the CRS must carry-out real-time

sensing of the RF environment such as in the case of the 5 GHz band to protect the Radiolocation service.

Beyond RF sensing, CRS need to be able to combine information from many sources including local regulations, local deployed channel usage, geolocation, and the various signal detection thresholds through which the CRS may sense the occupancy of channels in its neighborhood. The following examples will illustrate the need to rely on more than the results of RF sensing to protect the primary services.

2.1 Use of white space in TV broadcast bands

In the TV bands, the technology has historically required some channels to be left unused to provide guard spaces between the active channels. The guard channels are needed to accommodate TV receiver characteristics for near far (strong/weak) signals and adjacent channel performance. Some channels are also unused as there is limited TV service deployment in some geographic areas. The IEEE P802.22 committee² is working together with the broadcast community in the USA to develop practical means to allow operation of point-to-multipoint fixed license-exempt wireless broadband access systems in the TV band white space channels while fully protecting the broadcast services through the use of RF sensing as well as geolocation and incumbent databases. The IEEE P802.22 project was originally established to address the opportunity of using TV white space in the USA³ but the mandate of the project has been expanded to pursue worldwide applicability by including the 3 typical TV channel bandwidths: 6, 7, and 8 MHz, and thus making the standard potentially suitable for all the countries in the world.

The sensing requirement to protect TV broadcasting is much more demanding than in the case of protection of the radiolocation service in the 5 GHz bands. This is due to the fact that passive TV receivers need to be protected. Sensing needs to be made on the signal coming from the far-away transmitter is needed to protect receivers close-by. The broadcasters have identified that a threshold of -116 dBm at the input of the CRS is needed to provide sufficient protection for TV receivers located as far as the noise-limited contour of the DTV station. This corresponds to a safety margin of 24 dB to cover for potential extra signal blockage (i.e., hidden node) at the noise-limited contour. For a sensing RF front-end with 11 dB noise figure, this corresponds to detecting the presence of DTV at -21 dB SNR⁴.

The FCC has carried out an extensive number of laboratory and field tests on personal/portable devices that are also proposed for operation in the TV white spaces and it

² The IEEE 802.22 activities are outlined at <http://grouper.ieee.org/groups/802/22/>

³ Re: USA FCC NPRM Docket 04-186 as well as the First Report and Order and further NPRM Docket 06-15681 on use of TV bands white space by license-exempt wireless devices, similar to the Canadian policy for Remote Rural Broadband Systems described in a previous footnote.

⁴ 22-07-0112-01-0000_Sensing_Stochastic_Behavior.ppt available from <https://mentor.ieee.org/802.22/documents>

was found very difficult to reliably meet this threshold. In the case of the fixed point-to-multipoint broadband access systems for which the P802.22 standard is being developed, reliable detection of the TV stations may be made possible by the use of collaborative sensing where the sensing results from various user terminals are consolidated for a more reliable ‘network-wide’ decision on the availability of the current TV channel. Furthermore, extra information such as the geolocation of each of the sensing devices may be collected and used to query incumbent databases through the backhaul to confirm that these user terminals are outside the protected contour. These databases could be built in such a way that they would indicate to CRS the maximum EIRP allowed for each user terminal to avoid interference to TV services based on their geolocation. This way, all possible interference mechanisms may be taken into account such as co-channel, adjacent channel, alternate channel (i.e., taboo channels), and even 3rd order intermodulation beat (2a-b) that could affect TV and DTV reception.

Further to protect TV services, the new license-exempt devices will also need to protect the ‘low-power broadcast auxiliary systems’ such as wireless microphones that are allowed in these TV bands. Although the signal power from wireless microphones is very low and highly variable, protection of these auxiliary systems is expected to be possible with the help of a constant amplitude (i.e., 250 mW) beacon that will signal the presence of these microphones in the environment (see Task Group 802.22.1⁵). As long as the coverage distance of the beacon exceeds the interference distance of the license-exempt device (reciprocal signal propagation except for the different signal bandwidth), the wireless microphone service will be protected.⁶ Because of the highly dynamic behavior of these auxiliary systems, the channel move time required for protecting the wireless microphones in Task Group 802.22.1 is set to be 2 seconds.

2.2 Use of white space in FSS bands

The use of white spaces for terrestrial communications between the channels used by FSS ground stations has been investigated in parts of the 3.5 GHz band. Here, knowledge of the geographic location of the FSS earth stations is needed, as a necessary means to prevent interference from the CRS. The keep-out distance from these FSS earth stations are based on the high sensitivity of these FSS receivers, their limited out-of-channel filtering capabilities and the level of their antenna sidelobes near the horizontal plane.

Channel sensing and contention based protocols are also required to help alleviate interference among the cognitive systems operating in these white spaces. The protocols may, for example, be of two types, one that will detect other cognitive radio systems of any type and a second that only is capable of detecting systems of like type. Both the IEEE

⁵ The IEEE 802.22.1 activities are outlined at <http://grouper.ieee.org/groups/802/22/>

⁶ 22-08-0219-01-0001-tg1-required-detection-range-vs-protected-radii.ppt available from <https://mentor.ieee.org/802.22/documents>

P802.11y project⁷ and IEEE 802.16h project⁸ have provided a RLAN contention based radio systems (coordinated and uncoordinated) for application in the 3650-3700 MHz band on the basis of regulations in the USA (FCC Part 90), where the FSS earth stations are readily identifiable. The fundamental protection of the FSS stations is provided by knowing their geographic location. This approach involves "light licensing" in which all stations must be registered even though they may be sharing the channels with other "light" stations. If there were FSS station receivers that were difficult to identify (i.e. "nomadic" FSS receivers not a fixed locations), this solution would not be applicable.

2.3 Use of white space by co-primary services

In the 5 250-5 350 and 5 470-5 725 MHz bands, new power-limited communications systems are permitted to share the band with the incumbent RADAR systems of the Radiolocation Service. Based on the ITU Radio Regulations, these bands are allocated to the Radiolocation Service (RADAR) and to the Mobile Service on a primary basis. Recommendation ITU-R M.1739 provides the protection criteria for wireless access systems, including radio local area networks, operating in the mobile service in accordance with Resolution 229 (WRC-03) in the SE bands. However, mobile systems are required to confine their use to the areas of the bands where no radiolocation systems (RADARs) are active. The mobile systems must also vacate channels when new radiolocation systems (RADARs) come into operation.

The rules for use of these bands are thus similar in practice to the white space operation in the TV and FSS bands. The detection of the radiolocation systems signals is easier than in the case of the TV and FSS bands because of the signal power involved but is still technically challenging due to the short time duration of the RADAR signals and, for some systems, the irregularity of the transmitted pulses. Such signals can be difficult to distinguish from general noise or collisions among the autonomous communications systems. Techniques to analyse signals in addition to power measurement and pulse timing are required to successfully distinguish radiolocation systems signals from noise or intra-system interference. Comprehensive cognitive radio system techniques will need to be applied to make better use of the spectrum and, at the same time, avoid interference.

2.4 Intra-system co-channel interference mitigation and frequency reuse

Some CRS systems, in addition to sharing spectrum with primary users, have the additional capability of being able to self-organize and share occupied spectrum amongst themselves. The IEEE P802.16h project proposes a number of techniques by which CRS identify and quantify the degree of co-channel interference they cause amongst themselves. A 'coexistence protocol' is invoked which regulates spectrum usage amongst nearby CRS stations in a prescribed manner. These radio systems have the facility to actively trade

⁷ [The IEEE 802.11y activities are reported at http://grouper.ieee.org/groups/802/11/Reports/tgy_update.htm](http://grouper.ieee.org/groups/802/11/Reports/tgy_update.htm)

⁸ The IEEE 802.16h activities are reported at <http://wirelessman.org/le/index.html>

spectrum occupancy among themselves. The proposed 802.16h techniques rely on synchronization of the CRS community. This synchronisation permits the creation of system wide quiet spectrum occupancy sensing intervals during which interference from specific users is quantified and identified. Inter-system messages are used to relay the characteristics of interference events among the participating stations. The proposed techniques enhance the performance and spectrum utilization of spatial multiplexing (created by MIMO and/or adaptive antennas) by supporting frequency reuse and interference mitigation.

Similarly, in the case of the point-to-multipoint fixed broadband access systems proposed for use in the TV band white space, in addition to protecting the broadcast incumbents, RF sensing, spectrum etiquette and contention-based protocols are also considered, as part of the P802.22 standardization process, to help alleviate mutual interference among these fixed license-exempt systems to maximize the use of the TV white spaces.

3 Spectrum sensing techniques

There are several types of sensing techniques. First a sensing technique can be either signal specific or blind. A signal specific sensing technique is based on features of specific signal type. A blind sensing technique does not rely on features of a specific signal type. Typically, a blind sensing technique will be able to indicate that there is an RF signal in the channels but will not be able to identify its type. The signal specific sensing technique is able to identify the signal type. The signal specific sensing will tend to be more complex but will have the advantage of being more sensitive because of its knowledge of the signal to be sensed.

In some techniques, detection of an RF signal can begin using a lower sensitivity coarse sensing technique. If a signal is detected, a fine sensing technique can be used to verify the characteristics of the signal. If the coarse sensing technique was unable to detect a signal, then a fine sensing technique can also be used to sense for weaker signals. A coarse sensing technique may not be able to detect the presence of a signal at the required signal power but it may still be useful for detecting higher-power signals in a shorter period of time. A short sensing interval is desirable if there are a large number of channels to be sensed.

The performance for each of these sensing techniques can be expressed in terms of a SNR for which the probability of detection is greater or equal to, say, 99.9% while the probability of false alarm is kept at or below, say, 0.1% for a sensing time that does not exceed, say, 0.1 ms. Obviously, any change in any of these four variables will have an impact on the other three for a given sensing technique. For example, if the sensing time is increased, the minimum SNR at which the signal can be detected will tend to decrease. The sensing performance can be measured over various transmission channel conditions such as signal level variability, multipath, etc.)

Some sensing techniques are sensitive to uncertainty in the noise level of the sensing RF front-end. In these cases, the detector threshold is a function of the noise power estimate, so an error in that estimate can affect the detector performance. Hence, if the estimate of the noise power is within $\pm\Delta$ of the true noise power, then the achievable sensing threshold (SNR) is given for various values of the noise uncertainty parameter Δ .

3.1 *Blind sensing techniques*

A blind sensing technique does not depend on specific signal features. Three types of blind sensing techniques are described below: the energy detector, the eigenvalue sensing technique and the multi-resolution sensing technique.

3.1.1 Energy (power) detector^{9,10}

The energy, or power, detector is a simple method of quickly determining if a signal is present in the channel. Its performance in detecting very weak signals is however somewhat limited. Hence, it is classified as a coarse sensing technique.

To sense channel N with the energy detector technique the sensing receiver is tuned to channel N and the RF signal is converted to an intermediate frequency (IF) where a channel filter is used to filter out signals outside the channel N. After IF filtering the signal is down-converted to a base-band signal. The base-band signal is band-limited to the desired noise-equivalent bandwidth. The band-limited signal is complex (in-phase and quadrature) and is sampled at a frequency larger than its Nyquist frequency. The sampled signal is,

$$y(n) = x(n) + w(n)$$

Where $x(n)$ is the signal component and $w(n)$ is the noise component. The power of $x(n)$ is P_s and the power of $w(n)$ is P_N .

The test statistic for this sensing technique is,

$$T = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=1}^M y(n) y^*(n)$$

This is an estimate of the signal power. If the summation was not scaled by dividing by M then T would be an estimate of the signal energy. The choice of whether or not to scale by M does not affect the performance of the sensing technique. Since this is a rather simple test statistic it is possible to write an analytic formula for its probability density function. This is however not always possible for a sensing technique.

The mean and variance of the test statistic are,

$$E[T] = P_s + P_N$$

$$\text{var}[T] = \frac{(P_s + P_N)^2}{M}$$

For a large number of samples ($M \gg 1$), by the Central Limit Theorem, approximated as a Gaussian random variable,

⁹ 22-06-0075-00-0000_Performance-of-the-power-detector.ppt available from <https://mentor.ieee.org/802.22/documents>

¹⁰ 22-06-0134-00-000 Performance of the power detector with Noise Uncertainty

$$T \sim N\left(P_S + P_N, \frac{(P_S + P_N)^2}{M}\right)$$

Given this probability density function for the test statistic one can write a formula for the detector threshold based on the required false alarm probability,

$$\gamma = P_N \left[1 + \frac{Q^{-1}(P_{FA})}{\sqrt{M}} \right]$$

Where $Q(x)$ is the tail probability of a normalized zero-mean Gaussian random variable, and is given by,

$$Q(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_x^{\infty} e^{-x^2/2} dx$$

The sensing technique can be represented as a threshold comparison. If $T > \gamma$ then the channel is classified as occupied and if $T \leq \gamma$ then the channel is classified as vacant. The probability of detection depends on the signal power. The formula for the probability of detection is given by,

$$P_D = 1 - Q\left[\frac{\sqrt{M}}{P_S + P_N}(P_S + P_N - \gamma)\right]$$

The performance of this sensing technique in detecting weak signals relies heavily on accurate knowledge of the value of the noise power. This dependency on accurate knowledge of the noise power can be seen by writing our estimate of the noise power \hat{P}_N as the sum of the true noise power P_N and an error in the noise power estimate,

$$\hat{P}_N = P_N + P_E$$

The magnitude of the error in the noise power estimate is less than Δ , so we have,

$$-\Delta \leq P_E \leq \Delta$$

The threshold is set using the noise power estimate. And the actual probability of false alarm and probability of detection depend on the true noise power. If the noise power estimate \hat{P}_N is higher than the actual noise power P_N then the actual probability of false alarm and actual probability of detection will be lower than expected. This dependency on accurate knowledge of the noise power significantly limits the ability of this sensing technique to detect very weak signals ($SNR \ll 0dB$).

The primary performance metric for a sensing technique is the required SNR. For the following required SNR values the detector threshold has been set to give a probability of false alarm of 10%. The required SNR is the SNR at which the sensing technique has a probability of detection of at least 90% for all multipath conditions. The energy detector is not significantly impacted by multipath if the bandwidth of the channel is relatively wide (e.g., 6 MHz). The required SNR does depend on the noise uncertainty, so results are given for various values of noise uncertainty. The required SNR, for several sensing times and several values of noise uncertainty are given in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 — Required SNR for the Energy Detector

Sensing Time	$\Delta=0\text{dB}$	$\Delta=0.5\text{dB}$	$\Delta=1\text{dB}$
	Required SNR (dB)		
0.2 ms	-11	-5	-2.5
1 ms	-15	-6	-3
5 ms	-18	-6	-3

3.1.2 Eigenvalue sensing technique^{11,12,13}

The principle of this sensing technique is based on the fact that the statistics of an RF signal are likely to be different than that of noise. Such difference will be characterized by the eigenvalue distributions of the sample covariance matrix. This technique can be used without knowledge of the signal, the channel and the noise power. The same detection method is used for all types of signal and it is robust to channel multipath. No synchronization is needed and it avoids the noise uncertainty inherent to the energy detection technique reported in the previous section. This technique can use continuous or discontinuous time slots for sensing. The sensing threshold achieved depends on the level of noise from the sensing RF front-end, the cumulated sensing time, the probability of detection and the probability of false alarm. This technique can also be used over a number of contiguous channels to improve its sensitivity due to the nature of the gaps in RF power between adjacent channels.

Simulations have shown that for a probability of detection of 90% and false alarm of 10%, a DTV signal can be detected within 40 ms at SNR= -20 dB in 6 MHz or a wireless microphone can be detected within 10 ms at the same SNR in 200 kHz.

¹¹ 22-06-0119-01-0000_I2R-eigenvalue based sensing.ppt available from <https://mentor.ieee.org/802.22/documents>

¹² 22-06-187-03-0000 I2R Sensing 2

¹³ 22-07-0297-03-0000-Text-on-Eigenvalue-Based-Sensing.doc available from <https://mentor.ieee.org/802.22/documents>

3.1.3 Multi-resolution sensing technique^{14,15}

This sensing technique is based on a simplified real-time spectrum analysis of the RF signal where a narrowband filter sweeps the channel bandwidth and determines the spectrum envelope of the signal. A trade-off between the sensing time and the bandwidth of this sweeping filter or the coarseness of the frequency envelope can be made. The detection is based on the departure from the flat frequency representation of the noise seen from the resulting frequency envelope. Sensitivity can be improved by averaging the results over a number of sweeps, thus using a larger total sensing time. Additionally, the shape of the frequency envelope can be used to determine the type of signal detected.

Simulations have shown that for a probability of detection of 90% and false alarm of 10%, a DTV signal can be detected within 8 ms at SNR= -20 dB in 6 MHz with a 10 kHz sweeping filter.

3.2 *Signal specific sensing techniques*

A signal specific sensing technique relies upon the knowledge of specific signal features to improve signal detection.

3.2.1 RADAR detection

The first effort in developing signal specific sensing techniques took place as part of the detection of RADAR signals in the 5 GHz band. The RADAR operators were asked to define the waveform of the transmitted pulse, its duration and repetition rate. Techniques were then developed to identify these RF signals in addition to the power measurement and pulse timing in order to successfully distinguish the radiolocation systems signals from noise or intra-system interference. A very low rate of false positive detections is required to assure the CRS has access to channels for communications services as typically the regulations require a channel sensed with a primary signal must be kept out of CRS use for a lengthy interval. A high rate of false positive detections will very quickly block all the channels from CRS availability.

This sharing of the 5 GHz with radiolocation requires that the radio communications equipment must detect the operation of nearby RADAR systems, and stop using the channels if a RADAR signal is detected. The band sharing procedures are defined in the ITU-R WRC-03 Resolution 229 and ITU-R Recommendation M1652. These texts are supplemented by additional national and regional regulations for sharing and equipment testing (e.g. ETSI EN301-893 for the EU).

¹⁴ 22-07-0451-01-0000-text-on-mrсс.doc from <https://mentor.ieee.org/802.22/documents>

¹⁵ 22-07-0240-01-0000_MRSS_results.ppt available from <https://mentor.ieee.org/802.22/documents>

The method that has been endorsed by the ITU agreements to facilitate sharing between the radio communications and RADAR services is referred to as Dynamic Frequency Sharing (DFS). The ITU outlines a method and conditions for detecting periodic RADAR signals based on RADAR signal strength threshold, pulse width and periodicity.

The initial WRC-03 set an upper limit of the RADAR pulse width of about 20 microseconds which is less than the typical length of the radio communications signal bursts. This, in principle, enabled the radio communications to distinguish RADAR signals from radio communications signals and other noise. However, new RADAR technology is using pulses much longer than 20 microseconds, since these provide some advantages for the RADAR system for resolution, sensitivity and range. These longer pulses are about the same length as the typical radio communications signals making more difficult the distinction between communications signal collisions and the RADAR signals.

A radio communications receiver will see many signals in its band/channel that may mimic the RADAR pulse width and strength. These false signals occur due to RF noise or the transmissions from other radio communications devices in the band, and radio communications receivers have trouble distinguishing a real RADAR pulse sequence from this other noise and activity. These extra signals may be radio communications signals, noise (i.e. thermal and man-made artificial) or collisions between two or more radio communications signals or collisions between radio communications signals and RADAR signals. The decision that a RADAR signal has been detected is thus ambiguous. As a result, a significant number of pulses must be observed to reduce the false detection probability to an acceptable level for the radio communications operation.

The ITU method was designed to detect “conventional” RADAR systems by distinguishing the RADAR signals due to their pulse width and their periodicity. These characteristics are not shared by noise or other radio communications traffic. The ITU method is suitable for commercial RADAR systems that utilize traditional revolving beam antennas and have regular pulse emissions. However, many RADARs use a variety of pulse formats, durations and repetition intervals either for operational reasons or a desire to be covert (i.e. hard to detect). These systems are aperiodic and may also change their pulse formats, modulation and timing often and in a seemingly random way (see for example the description of the SENRAD: An Advanced Wideband Air-Surveillance Radar, Skolnik et al.; Naval Research Laboratory, IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON AEROSPACE AND ELECTRONIC SYSTEMS VOL. 37, NO. 4 OCTOBER 2001, page 1163). Hence the radio communications receiver cannot use the periodicity and limited range of pulse widths as a reliable means to distinguish these RADAR signals.

More sophisticated detection techniques have therefore been developed to more precisely identify radar pulses.

3.2.2 DTV signal detection

As part of the effort in developing the spectrum sensing capability of the Wireless Regional Area Network 802.22 systems, a number of techniques have been proposed to detect the

DTV signals. Unlike in the RADAR case where knowledge of the signal waveform was primarily used to avoid false positive, the knowledge of the DTV signal waveform is used to increase the sensitivity of the sensing process.

3.2.2.1 ATSC signal detection

A number of sensing schemes specific to the ATSC DTV signal have been proposed to try to provide detection at lower signal levels.

a) ATSC Signature Sequence correlation sensing technique

This sensing technique involves converting the received signal to baseband and correlating the signal with a signature sequence based on the Data Field Sync PN sequences. The output of the correlator is then processed to obtain a test statistic that is then compared to a threshold. The test Statistic can use a single ATSC Data Field, either field sync or data sync (the duration of a single ATSC data frame is 24.2 ms). The test Statistic can also use multiple ATSC Data Fields which would result in a sensing window of 48.4 ms (the duration of two ATSC data frames) or longer. It would then be possible to obtain better performance than with a single ATSC Data field but at the cost of a longer sensing interval¹⁶.

b) ATSC FFT-based Pilot Sensing Technique

The ATSC VSB signal has a pilot at the lower band-edge in a known location relative to the signal. The ATSC signal is converted down to IF and the pilot signal is filtered with a 40 kHz bandwidth. The filtered signal is then down-sampled and an FFT is applied to it. The maximum value of the largest squared signal bin is determined and compared to a threshold and its location is found to identify that it is indeed the pilot of an ATSC signal¹⁷.

c) ATSC Pilot Sensing Technique using high order statistics

The algorithm performs non-Gaussian check in the frequency domain in the vicinity of the pilot of the DTV. In the time domain, DTV signals show a Gaussian characteristic. However, in the frequency domain they are non-Gaussian. This characteristic is exploited to detect the signals in AWGN. The proposed technique on spectrum sensing using high order statistics may also be used to detect wireless microphone, DVB-T and other signals operating in the TV broadcasting bands. The 2048 point FFT used for OFDM demodulation is used for spectrum sensing.

¹⁶ Re: 22-06-0189-00-0000 An Evaluation of the PN Sequence based detection of DTV signals, 22-06-0243-05-0000 An ATSC Detector using Peak Combining, 22-07-0028-00-0000 Thomson signature based sensing.

¹⁷ Re: 22-07-0125-01-0000_Philips_pilot_detection_based_sensing_r1.ppt.

Use of Higher Order Statistics (HOS) is an efficient metric for detecting non-Gaussian signals at low SNRs. In particular, if we assume the noise to be a Gaussian random process, then all the cumulants of order greater than 2 are supposed to be zero. The higher order cumulants are compared with the power of second order moment. This is also known as bi-coherency tri-coherency etc. tests to determine if the received waveform belongs to DTV signal or the noise. Hence, a threshold needs to be set in order to make a decision as to whether the samples belong to signal or noise¹⁸.

c) ATSC PLL-based Pilot Sensing Technique

This sensor system employs two Frequency Tracking Blocks (FTBs). These blocks are designed to track a priori known frequency of the ATSC pilot at the Intermediate Frequency (IF) of the TV tuner output. The outputs are frequencies that the two FTBs are locked into at the given moment. In the absence of the pilot, or when the pilot energy is insufficient, the FTBs maintain their initial input preset values whereas they converge on the ATSC pilot frequency when the pilot is present¹⁹.

d) ATSC Pilot Covariance Sensing Technique:

This ATSC pilot detection scheme is based on an eigenvalue and covariance sensing technique. The principles and basic procedures of the algorithm are the same as for “covariance based sensing of wireless microphone”. The only difference is the choice of the filter. If a filter with 6 MHz bandwidth is chosen, the method is exactly the same as that for wireless microphone detection. Since ATSC DTV has a pilot tone with much higher power, it is better to use a narrowband filter to just catch the pilot tone. The location of the pilot tone spans about 59 kHz. A filter with slightly more than 60 kHz bandwidth is needed to catch the pilot tone in all cases²⁰.

e) Spectral Correlation Sensing Technique

In this sensing scheme, only spectral components from the received signals are used to extract information on incumbent user signals. All frequency components are obtained using the FFT of the signal sensed in the channel. Correlation detection measures the correlation between spectral signatures of the received signals and pre-stored signature information on various types of incumbent user signals. Thus more accurate information on target signals can be extracted at the receiver with relatively simple implementation. This spectral information for various incumbent signal types is stored in the detector²¹.

¹⁸ Re: 22-07-0359-00-0000_mody_spectrum_sensing_hos_1.ppt.

¹⁹ Re: 22-07-0125-01-0000_Philips_pilot_detection_based_sensing_r1.ppt.

²⁰ Re: 22-06-0118-00-0000_I2R-sensing.doc, 22-06-187-03-0000 I2R Sensing 2.

²¹ Re: 22-07-0034-02-0000 Huawei Simulation Results Spectral Correlation Sensing.

f) ATSC Cyclostationary Sensing Technique:

The ATSC signal is more appropriately modeled as cyclostationary, rather than stationary, due to its underlying periodicities. Since white Gaussian noise is not cyclostationary, this provides a way to separate the ATSC signal from noise²².

3.2.2.2 DVB-T signal detection

A Time-Domain Symbol Cross-Correlation based spectrum sensing algorithm (TDSC method) was developed to detect OFDM type signals. The algorithm makes use of the property that the mean of the TDSC function of two OFDM symbols is not zero if they have embedded the same frequency-domain pilot tones. Comparison was made with a spectrum sensing method which utilizes the Cyclic Prefix nature of the OFDM modulated signals as a reference²³.

3.2.3 Wireless microphone signal detection

This wireless microphone detection scheme is based on an eigenvalue and covariance sensing technique²⁴.

3.3 Interference mitigation techniques

Once the incumbent signal has been detected, the CRS system has to either vacate the channel within the required move time. The CRS may shift its operation to a backup channel that will have been cleared in advance using similar sensing techniques as for the operating channel. If there is no CRS operation in this backup channel, sensing can be done at any time rather than being limited to quiet periods of the CRS operation.

A more refined way of protecting the incumbent operation is to reduce the CRS device EIRP to the point where non-interfering co-existence is possible. This however requires a finer keep-out distance calculation based on geolocation of the CRS device and the

²² Re: 22-07-0133-00-0000 Thomson Cyclostationary based sensing.

²³ Re: 22-07-0364-00-0000_Thomson-pilot_based_sensing_DVB-T_OFDM.ppt, IEEE 802.22-08/0123r1 Text on Pilot Tone Based OFDM Detector, 22-06-0127-02-0000 Huawei Sensing Scheme for DVB-T.

²⁴ Re: 22-06-0118-00-0000_I2R-sensing.doc, 22-06-187-03-0000 I2R Sensing 2, 22-07-0325-00-0000 I2R-simulation for wireless microphone detection.

knowledge of the location of the incumbent protected contour as well as the agreed-upon propagation model to be used. This model also includes consideration of terrain data.

Moving out of a channel because the presence of an incumbent has been detected may not be sufficient to protect the primary operation. As an example, if a CRS operation can impact the incumbent operation in an adjacent channel, the sensing and Dynamic Frequency Selection action will have to consider any incumbent operation in the adjacent channel. By extension, if incumbent operation has to be protected in alternate channels, the same process will need to be extended to these channels (i.e., taboo channels) and either move of the CRS operation outside of its current channel or reduction of its EIRP will need to take place.

Consideration of adjacent and alternate channels makes the cognitive radio function much more complex because RF sensing has to take place over many more channels and the actions to avoid interference need to consider this increased number of channels.

4 Survey of the Bands Available for Spectrum Sensing

As stated in the introduction of this White Paper, spectrum availability is becoming more of an issue because of the ever-increasing number of wireless users and services, many of which require higher-and-higher data rates. The availability of spectrum to which sensing solutions could be applicable, which might be employed within the scope of Cognitive Radio (CR) or a wider Dynamic Spectrum Access (DSA) context, would help alleviate much of the pressure on the spectrum. However, the concept of spectrum sensing for dynamic spectrum usage, particularly in secondary spectrum access scenarios, generally conflicts with the rigid regulatory regime that has existed worldwide for some 100 years. Specifically, in order for regulators to reliably keep track of spectrum allocations, spectrum is generally not allowed to be dynamically shared among parties. The intended usage of spectrum, and often the owner (user) of the spectrum, is usually sacrosanct. Moreover, “owners” that have bought licenses for the spectrum, and parties that have the inherent right to spectrum for other reasons (e.g., emergency services, air traffic control and others), are often very concerned about the potential for interference in their spectrum decreasing the reliability of their services. Such parties often either reject outright the potential usage of opportunistic access via sensing solutions in their spectrum (in the view that it is logically unavoidable that such solutions will cause *some* interference, no matter how small), or demand a very high level of assurance that the sensing or other opportunity detection mechanism will be robust enough to ensure absolute minimum interference.

In the light of the above, a general conclusion which can be drawn is that, at least in terms of “beach-front property” spectrum (that in the MHz or low GHz range, which has favourable propagation characteristics), there is little or no spectrum to which DSA and associated sensing solutions can apply. However, there are interesting concepts in unlicensed spectrum to which sensing may (and in some respects, already does) apply, and there are a number of interesting topical developments that hold a strong possibility of changing current spectrum management regimes and allowing various DSA concepts to become a reality. The following sections discuss some of these developments.

4.1 Study of Prospective Bands

Given the switchover from analogue to digital television, huge swathes of premium “beach-front property” spectrum are becoming available for additional uses. This is because digital television is far more spectrally efficient than previous analogue formats. In response to concerted efforts to promote CRS and similar solutions (by, e.g., Microsoft, Google, Motorola, and others), the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) in the US has announced important rule changes that, among other issues, cover the possibility of “smart radios” (i.e., “cognitive radios”) being certified [1]. Moreover, in response to changing of TV channel allocations, the FCC has opened to the opportunity of secondary devices being certified for access to such channels [2]. Indeed, a rigorous testing regime is currently ongoing on a number of devices, to decide whether these devices should be authorised for

such access [3]. The conduct of these tests as “field trials” tends to suggest that it is only a matter of time before secondary access is allowed. In other countries such as the UK, there is also a drive for freer spectrum usage, apparent in the Office of Communications (Ofcom) Cognitive Radio Study [4], the Spectrum Usage Right concept [5], the Ofcom “Spectrum Framework Review” [6], and other efforts largely triggered by the “Review of Radio Spectrum Management” (also known as “The Cave Report”) [7]. Similar directions have been observed in elsewhere (see, e.g., [8] in Ireland, and [9] for the European Union in general).

A number of interesting standardisation efforts are being worked on related to spectrum sharing ideologies involving sensing. Within the IEEE, progress on the IEEE 802.22 standard is going well, the objective of which to improve spectrum utilization and wireless coverage by realizing Wireless Regional Area Networks (WRANs) through CRS [10]. In the US, these WRANs might opportunistically use the VHF and UHF TV bands between 54 and 862 MHz, the way for which has been paved for by [1], [2], [3]. Given the IEEE 802.22 adoption of an advanced collaborative sensing concept, the implication, dependent on acceptance by regulatory bodies, is for sensing solutions to be applicable to the secondary spectrum access technique. This is useful to highlight one of many possible benefits of CRS (through sensing solutions), in this case potentially providing broadband Internet access to isolated communities. Further efforts along the lines of spectrum sharing and DSA (often involving sensing) include the IEEE P1900 series of standards [11], which is working on, among other areas, solutions assisting spectrum management (IEEE P1900.4), and solutions assisting the practicality/effectiveness of sensing information exchange (IEEE P1900.6).

One related development in a direction similar to secondary access to TV bands is the US Rail Network’s request to the FCC to be able to increase the allowable “unlicensed” transmission power in the FM radio spectrum, in order to provide in-train communications. The increase in allowable power intended to use sensing mechanisms to ensure that it caused no interference to licensed users of the spectrum. This request was, however, rejected because it didn’t state exactly how such sensing mechanisms could be envisaged, or how the bands to be used would be chosen [12]. This reinforces the point that there is a high burden of proof required when it comes to ensuring that secondary access mechanisms through sensing do not cause unacceptable interference. Should such developments ever be accepted, they would open up the 87.5 to 108.0 MHz range for sensing solutions.

In recent years, there are a number of useful new developments in the regulatory regime, to which sensing might apply. For instance, unlicensed bands already have sensing mechanisms employed in them, in the form of collision avoidance mechanisms. Such bands include 40.66-40.7 MHz, 433.05-434.79 MHz, 902-928 MHz, 2.4-2.5 GHz, 5.725-5.875 GHz, and 24-24.25 GHz (among many others, of course with significant international and national variations), where of course, the extension of these sensing solutions to more of a primary/secondary access context, in certain locations, might be envisioned. “Light Licensing”, a novel concept in the US in the 3,650 to 3,700 MHz range [13], allows systems to share spectrum on a co-primary basis, whereby geographic location and signal sensing mechanisms are employed to ensure that no interference is caused among the

involved systems (either FSS or mobile). The IEEE 802.11y Working Group is one that has focused on such concepts, whereby should the “Light Licensing” concept become popular internationally; the scope is left open for it to apply in other bands in other countries.

Given the above observations, Figure 4.1 highlights some bands to which sensing solutions might conceivably be relevant in the short to medium term.

Figure 4.1 Some of the bands to which spectrum access solutions involving sensing might conceivably apply

4.2 Stability of Spectrum Holes

Most spectrum measurement campaigns so far have focused on “congestion” of frequency bands rather than occupancy pattern of the band. The result of such measurements are usually averaged over a time horizon, say 24 hours, which provides only rough information of idle periods in each band, such as band X, on average, is idle in Y percent of the time. Although in most released measurements such as by FCC, Ofcom, Spectrum Sharing Company, etc., in most bands the number Y is relatively high, there is no statistical model as to how often the primary user of the band re-occupies its licensed band. This information is critically important as it will affect the type of services and applications that can be provisioned using secondary access to each band. Also, many studies in the literature have investigated the “capacity” issues in secondary spectrum access scenarios, which provides another averaged view of the problem, this time over the distribution function of relevant stochastic parameters such as the channel or noise [14], [15]. Recently, a number of studies in the literature have tried to establish statistical models of spectrum hole availability, examples of which are [16], [17].

However, temporal analysis of spectrum holes by no means can provide a full picture of the available opportunities in a specific band. Spatial analysis will provide equally important perspective of stability of spectrum holes. Consider the case of IEEE 802.22-style

secondary access to the TV bands. The TV transmitters are broadcasting their signals continuously in time (assuming for simplicity of discussion 24 hour channels). The secondary spectrum access can happen whenever no TV receiver is close enough to the secondary transmitter to be interfered with. In such scenarios the spatial modelling of the spectrum holes is the only reliable means of determining the stability of spectrum holes, given a specific mobility pattern for the primary/secondary transmitters/receivers. In the IEEE 802.22 case, TV transmitters as the primary transmitters in the band as well as TV receivers are stationary similar to the 802.22 BSs, as the secondary transmitters.

In light of the above temporal and spatial analysis, a reliable band occupancy pattern, or the opposite, i.e., spectrum holes stability, can be studied more accurately. In cases where users, primary and secondary, follow a fixed or stationary distribution of temporal and spatial activity, the spectrum holes will have a relatively stable presence. As an example, since TV transmitters, after initial installation in a specific location, will operate for durations of the order of years, detected spectrum holes will follow similar life times. In contrast consider a cellular system as the primary occupant of a specific band. As the mobile users will randomly roam around a given cell (for example pedestrian users, vehicular users etc), starting a call session in random periods of time (for instance following a Poisson distribution) with random duration (for example based on Exponential distribution) the availability of each identified spectrum hole will only last for very short durations of time (say of the order milliseconds). Taking into account a multi-cell scenario will only increase the degree of complexity of spectrum hole stability analysis, but is sure to result in even shorter life expectancy for a given spectrum hole.

5 Use of Fragmented Frequency Spectrum for Wireless Broadband Communications

5.1 Description of the Approach

Today, several frequency bands are allocated to mobile and wireless communications. WRC 2007 discussed the potential identification of new frequency bands to mobile and wireless communications. In the following the basic idea of use of fragmented spectrum bands is presented without detailed figures on the today's allocated frequency bands.

The approach is based on a joint simultaneous use of different frequency bands in the frequency range of about 400 MHz up to about 6 GHz including the unlicensed frequency bands for WLAN applications. Figure 5.1 shows the basic map of frequency bands for mobile and wireless applications excluding broadcast spectrum, because this is currently not available for such applications.

Figure 5.1 Basic allocated frequency band for mobile and wireless applications (qualitative presentation)

There are now two basic concepts for a wideband communication system, which will be described in more detail in Section 5.2.

- Multi-band transmission system with several parallel transceivers for the different frequency bands, which are used simultaneously.
- Wideband receiver, which is processing the entire frequency band from about 400 MHz to about 6 GHz. The filtering should be done in the digital domain.

5.2 Basic Transceiver Concept

The two basic transceiver concepts are shown in Figures 5.2 and 5.3. The block diagrams are rather high-level in order to discuss the major impacts. Both concepts are explained only for the receiver section.

Figure 5.2 Multi-band received with parallel receivers for different bands

Figure 5.3 Wideband receiver for the entire band

A first basic assessment of the different concept is as follows:

Multi-band receiver:

- The RF band pass filter per branch has a bandwidth corresponding to the allocated band. This filter is also needed as anti-aliasing filter.
- The channel filtering per link will be done in the digital domain.

- This concept will be feasible. It is similar to today's multi-band terminals.
- Several RF branches are needed, which need volume (RF filters).
- The dynamic range should be feasible due to the limitation to useful bands and the avoidance of adjacent disturbing signals as much as possible due to RF filtering.
- However, this concept is rather complex.

Wideband receiver:

- The RF band pass is needed as anti-aliasing filter for wideband sampling. Its bandwidth covers the entire receiver bandwidth.
- The channel filtering per link will be done in the digital domain.
- This concept requires very wideband RF components.
- A very high sampling rate is needed.
- A much higher dynamic range is necessary in order to mitigate the impact of strong adjacent disturbing signals (e.g. broadcast and radar signals), which are within the wide input RF bandwidth but outside of one of the useful frequency bands.
- This requires A/D-converters with very high resolution and linearity.
- The RF components have to be very linear and to be able to handle high-amplitude signals.

There are two basic concepts for the implementation of the wideband receiver according to Figure 5.3:

- Either the A/D-conversion is performed directly in the RF domain with down-conversion (mixing) and channel filtering in the digital domain (version A) or
- the wideband RF signal is down-converted in an IQ-mixer in the analogue domain to the base band and the I- and Q-channel are separately A/D-converted according to the band pass sampling theorem (version B) [31].

In the case of a general asymmetric input signal and band pass transfer function with respect to the center frequency Figure 5.4 shows the two basic receiver implementations [31].

Version A

Version B

Figure 5.4 Potential receiver implementations

5.3 Brief Investigation of Several Topics Affecting the System Design

The following investigation is mainly made for the wideband concept. The figures can easily be transformed to the multi-band concept. However, due to the different band pass filters the impact of interference and other issues is basically smaller than in the wideband concept.

5.4 Frequency Dependent Path Loss

The frequency dependence of the path loss $L(f_c)$ [dB] on the carrier frequency f_c depends on the actual propagation conditions. For free-space propagation the frequency dependence corresponds to [3, pp. H12 and H30]

$$L(f_{c,2}) - L(f_{c,1}) = 20 \cdot \log\left(\frac{f_{c,2}}{f_{c,1}}\right) \text{ [dB]} \quad (1)$$

With increasing carrier frequency the path loss is increasing quadratic. For shadowing propagation the increase of path loss is bigger with about 25 – 30 dB/decade for suburban areas and about 30 dB/decade for urban areas [4 – 11].

$$L(f_{c,2}) - L(f_{c,1}) = 30 \cdot \log\left(\frac{f_{c,2}}{f_{c,1}}\right) \text{ [dB]} \quad (2)$$

For some propagation conditions this increase may be even bigger. Figure 5.5 show this dependence in the frequency range 0.4 to 6 GHz. The relative path loss is normalized to 400 MHz.

Figure 5.5 Relative path loss versus carrier frequency

In the upper frequency bands the radio channel shows a significantly higher path loss. This results directly in a significant reduction of range for the upper bands. Within the bandwidth under discussion a huge difference in path loss has to be considered.

5.5 Doppler Frequency and Doppler Spectrum

Due to moving receivers, transmitters and/or movements in the environment the radio channel is time-variant. This is described by the Doppler shift f_d or in the case multi-path

propagation by a Doppler spectrum $S_E(f)$, which represents the different Doppler shifts from different received waves from different directions [21; 30]. Eq. (3) shows the Doppler shift versus mobile speed v , the carrier wave length λ , the speed of light c_0 , the angle of arrival θ between the mobile direction and the incoming wave:

$$f_d = \frac{v}{\lambda} \cdot \cos \theta = \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot f_c \cos \theta = f_{d,m} \cdot \cos \theta \quad . \quad (3)$$

The maximum Doppler shift is

$$f_{d,m} = \pm \frac{v}{c_0} \cdot f_c \quad (4)$$

with the Doppler spectrum under the assumption of a uniform distribution of incoming waves from all directions

$$S_{E_z}(f) = \frac{1.5}{\pi \cdot f_{d,m} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{f - f_c}{f_{d,m}}\right)^2}} \quad \text{for} \quad -f_{d,m} \leq f - f_c \leq f_{d,m} \quad . \quad (5)$$

Outside of this range the Doppler spectrum is zero. The maximum relative Doppler shift in the frequency range 0.4 to 6 GHz is directly proportional to the ratio of carrier frequencies (Figure 5.6):

$$\frac{f_{d,m2}}{f_{d,m1}} = \frac{f_{c2}}{f_{c1}} \quad . \quad (6)$$

Figure 5.6 Relative maximum Doppler shift

In the upper frequency bands the radio channel shows a significantly higher time variance than in the lower bands, which requires a higher update rate for adaptation algorithms such as equalization and power control. This may result in higher overhead in the upper bands for signaling.

5.6 Effective Noise Power

The thermal noise density power at an absolute temperature of 300 K corresponds to $N_0 = -174$ dBm/Hz [21]. Including the receiver noise figure F the effective noise power within the receive bandwidth B follows as:

$$N_{eff} = N_0 \cdot B \cdot F \quad (7)$$

With a receiver noise figure $F = 5$ dB and the entire receive bandwidth $B = 6$ GHz – 0.4 GHz = 5.6 GHz the total noise power is given by

$$N_{eff, total} = N_0 [dBm/Hz] + 10 \cdot \text{Log}(B_{total}) [dBHz] + F [dB] = -71.5 dBm \quad (8)$$

This noise power is significantly below the power levels of the receiver, where nonlinear effects might be expected. The noise power per band and the noise power density needs to be investigated.

Under the assumption that the smallest signal bandwidth after base band filtering equals $B_{min, ch} = 1.25$ MHz the effective noise power follows as

$$N_{eff, 1.25MHz} = N_0 [dBm/Hz] + 10 \cdot \text{Log}(1.25MHz) [dBHz] + F [dB] = -108. dBm \quad (9)$$

This might be the smallest noise power level, which has to be considered for the dynamic range of the receiver.

5.7 Receiver Input Signal and Impact of Nonlinearities in the Analogue Receiver Components

5.7.1 Input Signal

The receiver input signal is rather complex. After the RF band pass, which is also needed as anti-aliasing filter, useful signals in different part-bands and disturbing signals from other services between the different part-bands are present. Such disturbing signals may have very high transmit power such as broadcast and radar signals.

The RF pre-selection band pass filter transfers all receive signals $u_r(t)$ according to eq. (11) within the RF reception band according to its transfer function.

All signals out of the RF reception band $u_{r,out}(t)$ are attenuated with respect to the band pass characteristic. – These signals are not considered in the following. –

Useful receive signals within part-band j:

$$u_{r,band,j}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{I(j)} u_{r,j,i}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{I(j)} a_{r,j,i}(t) \cdot \sin(\omega_{r,j,i} \cdot t + \varphi_{r,j,i}(t))$$

Useful receive signals in all part-bands:

$$u_{r,useful}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^J u_{r,band,j}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{i=1}^{I(j)} u_{r,j,i}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{i=1}^{I(j)} a_{r,j,i}(t) \cdot \sin(\omega_{r,j,i} \cdot t + \varphi_{r,j,i}(t)) \quad (10)$$

Disturbing signals between part-bands:

$$u_{r,disturbing}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K u_{r,k}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K a_{r,k}(t) \cdot \sin(\omega_{r,k} \cdot t + \varphi_{r,k}(t))$$

The total receive signal after the receive RF band pass including noise is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} u_r(t) &= u_{r,useful}(t) + u_{r,disturbing}(t) + n(t) = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{i=1}^{I(j)} u_{r,j,i}(t) = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{i=1}^{I(j)} a_{r,j,i}(t) \cdot \sin(\omega_{r,j,i} \cdot t + \varphi_{r,j,i}(t)) + \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^K u_{r,k}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K a_{r,k}(t) \cdot \sin(\omega_{r,k} \cdot t + \varphi_{r,k}(t)) + \\ &+ n(t) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Even if the sampling of the input signal is performed directly in the band pass domain without a mixing process to an intermediate frequency (IF), the signal to be detected has to be transformed to the base band domain in the digital signal processing. This does only correspond to one possibility of implementation. Therefore, issues like image rejection and reciprocal mixing etc. have to be considered in general.

5.7.2 Receiver Nonlinearities

In a simplified description the analogue active part of the receiver may be represented by a nonlinear characteristic (Taylor series):

$$u_m(t) = c_0 + c_1 \cdot u_r(t) + c_2 \cdot u_r^2(t) + c_3 \cdot u_r^3(t) + \dots \quad (12)$$

Under overload conditions additional signals are generated due to distortion and intermodulation, which may disturb the demodulation process.

- For one input signal a reduction of amplification due to nonlinear distortion for a cubic characteristic with increasing input signal amplitude (compression) occurs [32].
- For – in minimum – two input signals (useful plus disturbing signal) intermodulation products result in reduction of the output signal amplitude of the useful signal for increasing disturbing signal input amplitude (desensitization or blocking) [32].
- For multiple input signals intermodulation products are generated.

The receiver nonlinearity can be characterized by the 2nd and 3rd order intercept points.

5.8 Image Rejection

The RF band pass is needed for some pre-selection with respect to the entire input signal and as image reject filter. However, due to the very complex input signal within the bandwidth of the RF band pass according to eq. (11) disturbing signals with potentially high transmit power cannot be avoided directly by a band pass filter in front of the active receiver components (low noise RF amplifier, potential mixers). Such disturbing signals may be reduced by dedicated notch filters as part of the RF pre-selection filter.

In the case of a mixing process with an IF f_{IF} , different input signals at different receive carrier frequencies f_r may lead to nonlinear distortion and harmonics of the local oscillator frequency f_{LO} to this same IF-range.

$$f_{IF} = |m \cdot f_r \pm n \cdot f_{LO}| \quad \text{with } m, n = 1, 2, 3 \dots \quad (13)$$

Therefore, the complex input signal may result in the active and usually nonlinear receiver components in

- linear spurious reception due to the mixing process ($m = 1$)
- image reception
- reciprocal mixing
- nonlinear spurious reception due to receiver nonlinearities ($m > 1$)
- overload, cross modulation, limiting and blocking
- possible spurious reception frequencies (one signal at receiver input)

In the case of $f_{LO} > f_{IF}$ and no overloading of the RF pre-amplifier and mixer ($m = 1$) two possible receive frequencies per local oscillator harmonic (image reception) may be observed:

$$f_{r,n/1} = n \cdot f_{LO} - f_{IF} \quad \text{and} \quad f_{r,n/2} = n \cdot f_{LO} + f_{IF} \quad .(14)$$

Usually, contributions resulting from local oscillator harmonics ($n > 1$) are negligible. Therefore, the RF pre-selection band pass filter has to avoid signals at frequencies $2 f_{IF}$ apart from useful signals with (c.f. Figure 5.7):

$$2 \cdot f_{IF} \geq B_{RF} \quad . \quad (15)$$

Figure 5.7 Relation between B_{RF} and f_{IF}

In the case of a very big RF bandwidth in the order of $B_{RF} = 5.6$ GHz the IF has to be $f_{IF} > 2.8$. The requirements on the pre-selection filter slope are relaxed for increasing f_{IF} . For very wideband RF band pass filter no high stop-band attenuation can be expected. Therefore, the main channel selection with high stop-band attenuation performed in IF- or base band stage to reduce the effective receiver noise bandwidth and to avoid overload in the main IF amplification due to high power out of IF band signals. However, this may not be possible in the concept according to Figure 5.3, where the main filtering is done in the digital domain. Therefore, the analogue receiver has to show a high resistance against overload conditions.

5.9 Receiver Performance (Desensitization, Blocking, Intermodulation)

The basic performance of the receiver is summarized in Figure 5.8 [21].

Figure 5.8 Receiver performance

A: Receiver sensitivity due to noise, no interference.

B – C: Impact of reciprocal mixing, required useful signal has to be increased proportionally to additional noise.

C – C': Limit due to cross modulation for modulated interfering signal.

D: Maximum level of useful input signal for one disturbing signal with same amplitude, in-band intermodulation products and/or harmonics determine output signal/intermodulation-ratio.

E – E': For two input signals 3rd order intermodulation products proportional to third power of disturbing signal level.

F – F': For two input signals 2nd order intermodulation products proportional to second power of disturbing signal level (less important due to RF pre-selection).

IPIP3: Construction of 3rd order intercept point.

IPIP2: Construction of 2nd order intercept point.

5.10 Reciprocal Mixing and Receiver Noise Figure

The receiver is not only affected by thermal noise and receiver internal additional noise sources. In a system with several carrier input signals in front of the mixer reciprocal mixing especially in the RF stage of the receiver may play a significant role. Figure 5.9 shows the effect of reciprocal mixing [32].

Figure 5.9 Reciprocal mixing

The three figures are explained in the following:

- Top: Difference mixing with high-side injection and down conversion based on the difference frequency between the local oscillator and the received signal.
- Middle: Extension of the top figure when the oscillator noise is significant. The phase noise is down converted towards the IF.
- Bottom: Reciprocal mixing occurs when an undesired signal (adjacent channel) mixes with the oscillator noise to produce additional noise in IF pass band.

Reciprocal mixing results in an additional noise figure F_{RM} proportional to the amplitude of the disturbing signal (adjacent channel) within the RF pass band and the single side band oscillator phase noise [3]. However, F_{RM} is independent of the receiver noise figure.

$$F_{RM} [dB] = P_s [dBm] + \Phi_e(f) [dBc/Hz] + 174 [dBm/Hz] \quad (16)$$

The additional noise components due to the oscillator phase noise increase the effective receiver noise figure with increasing number of adjacent disturbing carriers. The resulting receiver noise figure for N input signals follows as:

$$F_{receiver, res} [dB] = 10 \log \left\{ 10^{F_{receiver} [dB]/10} + \sum_{i=1}^N 10^{F_{RMi} [dB]/10} \right\} \quad (17)$$

In the case of the wideband received according to Figure 5.3 there is a high likelihood for many high power disturbing signals. These relations have to be considered in the design of the RF filters and the local oscillator phase noise requirements. The relation in eq. (16) is shown in Figure 5.10 [21].

Figure 5.10 Additional noise figure F_{RM} due to reciprocal mixing

When the receive level of an adjacent carrier is below -44 dBm and the oscillator phase noise reaches -130 dBc/Hz, the additional noise figure due to reciprocal mixing would be $F_{RM} = 0$ dB. The effect of reciprocal mixing can be reduced further by oscillators with low phase noise and for low effective adjacent channel amplitude.

The receiver chain noise figure (Friis formula) according to [21] follows as

$$F_{receiver,res} = F_1 + \frac{F_{add,2}}{L_{v1}} + \frac{F_{add,3}}{L_{v1} \cdot L_{v2}} + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^N 10^{F_{RMi} [dB]/10} \tag{18}$$

with, e.g;

- index 1 – antenna cable plus image reject filter,
- index 2 – pre-amplifier and
- index 3 – mixer (without reciprocal mixing).

A high receiver sensitive requires

- low noise first receiver stages (F_1 and $F_{add,2}$) plus high amplification ($L_{v1} \cdot L_{v2}$) to reduce the impact of mixer conversion loss and
- oscillators with low phase noise to reduce the impact of reciprocal mixing.

The additional noise figure F_{RM} due to reciprocal mixing increases with an increasing number N and amplitude of input signals independent of the receiver noise figure $F_{receiver}$ without reciprocal mixing. On the other hand a reduced impact of intermodulation is achieved through a low gain RF amplifier. Therefore, a trade-off between the receiver sensitivity and the impact of intermodulation has to be implemented for overall optimal performance.

5.11 Band Pass Filters and Filter Slope for Stop-band Attenuation

The following general description of the RF band pass filter is done for lossless filters. The feasibility concerning

- insertion loss,
- achievable stop band attenuation,
- group delay distortion,
- possible filter order,
- filter size and
- cost

is not considered.

The overall filtering is usually distributed between the base band, the IF and the RF domain. In the RF band the maximum receive power at the input of the RF low noise amplifier has to be sufficiently low to avoid blocking of the receiver. As shown in Section 4.9 very high input signal amplitudes from disturbing signals within the wideband band pass bandwidth have to be expected.

The low pass (LP) and the band pass (BP) domain are related by the LP-BP-transformation with the band pass cut-off frequencies f_{c1} and f_{c2} [33; 34], the normalizing frequency

$$f_n = \sqrt{f_{c1} \cdot f_{c2}} \quad (19)$$

the normalized band pass frequency

$$F_{BP} = \frac{f}{f_n} \quad (20)$$

and the normalized low pass frequency for filter design

$$F_{LP} = \frac{1}{F_{BP,c2} - F_{BP,c1}} \cdot \left(F_{BP} - \frac{1}{F_{BP}} \right) \quad (21)$$

The RF frequency range is allocated between $f_{c1} = 0.4$ to $f_{c2} = 6$ GHz. With an assumed reference RF bandwidth of

$$f_{c2} - f_{c1} = 5.6 \text{GHz} \quad (22)$$

the relative RF bandwidth with an average carrier frequency of

$$\frac{f_{c1} + f_{c2}}{2} = 3.2 \text{GHz} \quad (23)$$

is in the order of 175 %, which results in a very low Q-factor. The RF filter should be designed according to Figure 5.3 as band pass filter for the entire receive and transmit band. The channel filtering should be performed in the digital base band or possibly IF domain. Due to the very high relative bandwidth the RF band pass shows a very asymmetric attenuation slope for the upper and the lower bound with a different but low increase in stop band attenuation.

Under the assumption that the maximum attenuation in the pass band at the band edge corresponds to 3 dB, the RF band edge frequencies 0.4 and 6 GHz correspond in the equivalent LP domain to the band edge frequency $f_{LP,c} = 2.8$ GHz corresponding to the normalized frequency $F_{LP,c} = 1$. The following figures apply:

$$f_n = 1.549 \text{GHz}$$

$$f_{c1} = 400 \text{MHz} \quad F_{BP,c1} = 0.258 \quad (24)$$

$$f_{c2} = 6 \text{GHz} \quad F_{BP,c2} = 3.873 \quad .$$

In Figure 5.11 the equivalent normalized LP frequency in the stop band is presented for the lower and the upper slope of the wideband RF band pass.

Figure 5.11 Normalized LP frequency for the lower and upper bound slope of the RF band pass

At the upper bound a reasonable attenuation can only be achieved for very high frequency separation. Therefore, disturbing signals beyond 6 GHz have to be taken into account. In addition, the band pass does not serve as anti-aliasing filter. At the lower bound a reasonable stop band attenuation can be achieved for a separation of several 100 MHz. However, also here disturbing signals below 400 MHz have to be considered.

In the case of a Butterworth filter of the order n the attenuation follows the function:

$$a(F_{LP})[dB] = 10 \cdot \log(1 + F_{LP}^{2 \cdot n}) \quad (25)$$

Figure 5.12 shows the achievable attenuation versus offset frequency from the band edge for a Butterworth filter of the order of n . Here a filter order $n = 6$ is assumed.

Figure 5.12 Attenuation at the lower and upper bound slope of the RF band pass

The low attenuation at the upper bound will result is serious problem with disturbing signal above 6 GHz.

5.12 Maximum Input Signal

Within the RF bandwidth very strong disturbing signals such as broadcast of radar signals may occur, which potentially impact the receiver performance. Therefore, the receiver has to have a sufficient dynamic range in order to avoid overload conditions.

In a simplified worst-case estimation a broadcast transmitter with the following parameters is assumed:

- Transmit power: 20 kW
- Broadcast transmitter antenna gain: 20 dBi
- Terminal antenna gain: 0 dBi
- Distance between transmitter and receiver: 300 m
- Transmitter carrier frequency: 800 MHz

For free space propagation close to the broadcast transmitter according to Figure 5.13 and eq. (26) the maximum receive power follows as:

$$P_r = P_t \cdot \frac{G_t \cdot G_r \cdot \lambda_0^2}{(4\pi d)^2} = P_t \cdot \frac{G_t \cdot G_r \cdot c_0^2}{(4\pi d)^2 \cdot f_c^2} = S_r \cdot A_{er} \quad . \quad (26)$$

Figure 5.13 Interference scenario between a broadcast transmitter and a mobile terminal

This scenario results in a maximum receive power in the order of

$$P_{r,max} = 2.8mW \quad \text{corresponding to 4.5 dBm} \quad (27)$$

at the terminal. Under these conditions the receiver should not show desensitization or blocking as well as nonlinear distortion.

5.13 Sampling Theorem for Both Receiver Versions

Figure 5.4 presents the two versions of the receiver implementation:

- Version A with direct sampling in the RF domain,
- Version B based on the band pass sampling theorem.

Both versions have a different impact on the sampling rate.

Under the assumption of an ideal rectangular RF band pass as anti-aliasing filter the following sampling rates are necessary [31]. – However, such filters are not feasible and with respect to Section 4.8 the attenuation at the upper bound is very small. –

- Version A: Maximum signal frequency, which needs to be sampled in the RF domain corresponds to $f_{max} = 6$ GHz. This results in a minimum sampling rate of 12 G-samples/s for real signal. In this case an A/D-converter with a sampling rate of 12 G-samples/s is required.
- Version B: According to the band pass sampling theorem for a band pass bandwidth $B = 5.6$ GHz the sampling rate per I- and Q-channel corresponds to two times the RF

bandwidth B. Therefore, the sampling rate for the complex base band signals corresponds to 5.6 G-samples/s or to 5.6 + 5.6 G-samples/s for the I- and Q-channel. In this case two A/D-converters with a sampling rate of 5.6 G-samples/s each are needed.

5.14 A/D-Converter Dynamic Range and Output Data Rate

The A/D-converter has a limited resolution. It generates quantization noise. According to [35] the signal/noise-ratio between the effective values of a sinusoidal input signal $U_{s,eff}$ and the triangular quantization error $U_{q,eff}$ for a resolution of N bits is given by:

$$\left. \frac{S}{N} \right|_{\text{quantization}} = 20 \cdot \log \frac{U_{s,eff}}{U_{q,eff}} [dB] = N \cdot 6dB + 1.8dB \quad . \quad (28)$$

The quantization noise should be below the effective receiver noise level in order not to increase the effective noise figure. With respect to [21] the A/D-converter dynamic range D_{ADC} follows under this condition as

$$D_{ADC} = N \cdot 6dB - (5 \text{ to } 10)dB \quad . \quad (29)$$

With respect to the maximum input power according to eq. (27) and the minimum noise power for narrow band signals in eq. (9) a minimum dynamic range of 112.5 dB is needed. Under the assumption that for the narrow band signal with 1.25 MHz carrier bandwidth (like TD-SCDMA, cdma2000) spread spectrum modulation may be applied, receive signals below the noise level may be detected using processing gain. Then the required dynamic range is in the order of

$$D_{ADC} = 120 \text{ to } 130dB \quad . \quad (30)$$

This corresponds to a required A/D-converter resolution of 21 to 24 bit.

This results with Section 4.10 in the following data rates for the output signal of the A/D-conversion before digital signal processing:

- Version A: Minimum sampling rate of 12 G-samples/s for real signal with an A/D-converter resolution of 21 to 24 bit provides a data rate for digital signal processing of

$$252 \text{ to } 288 \text{ Gbps (31.5 to 36 Gbyte/s)} \quad . \quad (31)$$

- Version B: Minimum sampling rate for the complex base band signals corresponding to 5.6 + 5.6 G-samples/s for the I- and Q-channel provides a data rate for digital signal processing of

$$117 + 117 \text{ to } 134 + 134 \text{ Gbps (2} \cdot 14.6 \text{ to } 2 \cdot 16.75 \text{ Gbyte/s)} \quad . \quad (32)$$

Such high data rate signals would need to be processed in the receiver.

5.15 A/D-Converter Performance Development

There is a relation between the sampling rate and the resolution of the A/D-converters. Figure 5.14 shows the currently (status 2006) valid limiting curve between the number of bits versus sampling rate. With respect to the requirements in Sections 5.10 and 5.11 there will be no A/D-converters in the foreseeable future available, which will support

- a sampling rate in the order of several GHz and
- a dynamic range in the order of 120 to 130 dB.

Basic limitations for the progress of the development of AD-converters are also confirmed by Analog Devices, Inc. in [36]. According to [36] no significant progress is expected in the coming year. New processes for semiconductor technology will be needed.

Figure 5.14 Resolution-bandwidth tradeoff

For a potentially expected channel bandwidth of about 100 MHz with an ideal rectangular channel filter for anti-aliasing purposes in minimum 100 M-samples for the complex base band signal or 100 + 100 M-samples for the real and imaginary component are required. Such sampling rates correspond with Figure 5.14 to a maximum 11 bits and thereby an

A/D-converter dynamic range in the order of 71 to 76 dB. Therefore, adjacent carrier interference has to be avoided in front of the A/D-converter by using a channel bandpass filter in the IF-domain in order to reduce the necessary dynamic range. In addition, an AGC (Automatic Gain Control) in the RF receiver in the IF-domain after channel filtering is required.

In conclusion, if fragmented frequency spectrum should be applied in order to support wideband systems with a total channel bandwidth in the order of 100 MHz, a receiver concept according to Figure 5.2 is a feasible solution. A wideband receiver according to Figure 5.3 will not be feasible due to the huge necessary dynamic range. In the ideal case the necessary channel bandwidth should be available in a single consecutive frequency block.

5.16 Wrap up

First investigations have already been made in the WINNER project [35] under less challenging requirements. A more in-depth investigation will require significant effort to look at the different aspects.

However, the available information on the expected performance of A/D-converters in terms of number of bits versus sampling rate provide a clear indication that due to the strict limitations (Figure 5.14) for the achievable dynamic range and sampling rate only a receiver concept according to Figure 5.2 will be feasible. The impact of adjacent channels has to be avoided by channel filtering to reduce the necessary dynamic range. In the ideal case the number of receiver chains per transmission channel should be as small as possible; therefore, a single block of spectrum is desired.

The concept of a very wideband receiver according to Figure 5.3, which may be affected by strong adjacent carrier signals seems not to be feasible.

6 Conclusions

This white paper discussed spectrum sensing and receiver designs for fragmented spectrum assignments and their usefulness in future wireless communications.

We showed that it is possible to apply spectrum sensing in various bands. A practical example of sensing is, according to the ITU-R, the sharing of the 5 GHz radiolocation band by license-exempt radio local area network systems. In this band, new power-limited communications systems are permitted to share the band with the incumbent RADAR systems in the Radiolocation Service with the requirement that proper detection of the primary user is made and that in such cases, the low-power license-exempt devices would quickly move out of the frequency range used by the RADAR system. Since then, cognitive radio systems (CRS) have been considered in many other applications to allow re-use of the spectrum white spaces. Examples of potential applications include additional spectrum use within the TV broadcast bands and the use of the 5 GHz band by co-primary services that could be similar in practice to the use of white space. The stations of the primary service in most of these cases have a fixed location, a fixed area of coverage and a predictable channel usage. These characteristics help create the opportunity to use this spectrum as white space.

Then we went on to investigate various types of sensing techniques. There are two types of sensing techniques, either signal specific or blind. Under the first category, we discussed energy detector technique, eigenvalue sensing and multi-resolution sensing techniques. While in the latter, we addressed detection techniques for Radar, DTV and wireless microphones. We found that the performance for each of these sensing techniques can be expressed in terms of a SNR for which the probability of detection is greater or equal to, while the probability of false alarm is kept at or below for a given sensing time.

Furthermore, we provided a very useful survey of bands available for spectrum sensing. We have established that it is important to provide spatial and temporal analysis of stability of spectrum holes and thus construct a reliable band occupancy pattern.

Finally, we examined the basic concept of a wideband receiver for the use of fragmented frequency spectrum for broadband application over IMT-Advanced systems. Mainly, the major issues were addressed, which need further evaluation such as:

- Frequency Dependent Path Loss
- Doppler Frequency and Doppler Spectrum
- Effective Noise Power

- Impact of receiver nonlinearities due to very high disturbing input signals within the receive band
- RF band pass filtering for image rejection, anti-aliasing and rejection of strong disturbing signal within the RF receiver bandwidth
- Estimation of required receiver dynamic range
- Necessary dynamic range of the A/D-converter
- Data rate for digital signal processing.

These issues have to be evaluated for potential future implementation with respect to technology roadmaps for

- RF receiver components,
- A/D-converters and
- available signal processing power

with respect to implementation cost, form factor and power consumption.

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Imprint

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The WWRF **Outlook** Visions and research directions for the Wireless World

ISSN 1662-615X is published non-periodically by the Wireless World Research Forum
<http://www.wireless-world-research.org>

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